

m, ArH). For other compounds, mol. formulae, yield (%) and m.p., (°C) are: **2a**, $C_{11}H_9NO_4Br_2$, 76, 64; **2b**, $C_{11}H_9NO_4BrCl$, 87, 54; **2c**, 76, 58; **2d**, $C_{13}H_{15}NO_4$, 79, 44; **2f**, $C_{12}H_{11}NO_4Br_2$, 88, 62; **2g**, 78, b.p. 290°; **2h**, $C_{12}H_{11}NO_4BrCl$, 87, 62.

Preparation of 3a-h: A mixture of **2b** (0.02 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 0.056 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 30 min. On cooling white needle shaped crystals that separated were recrystallised from ethanol to give **3b**, (75%), m.p. 131° (Found: C, 33.60; H, 2.10; N, 13.05. $C_9H_7O_3N_3BrCl$ requires: C, 33.80; H, 2.19; N, 13.15%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 200 (NHNH₂) and 1 680 cm^{-1} (CO-NH); δ 2.5 (2H, br s, NH₂), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH₂), 7.0–7.5 (2H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, br s, NH). For other compounds, mol. formulae, yield (%), m.p. (°C) are: **3a**, $C_9H_7N_3O_3Br_2$, 78, 224; **3c**, 77, 112; **3d**, $C_{11}H_{13}N_3O_3$, 73, 82; **3e**, $C_{10}H_{10}N_3O_3Br$, 80, 171; **3f**, $C_{10}H_9N_3O_3Br_2$, 70, 84; **3g**, 78, 78; **3h**, $C_{10}H_9N_3O_3BrCl$, 76, 187.

Preparation of 4: A mixture of compound **3g** (0.001 mol) and ammonium acetate (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for **4h**, when the yellow colour of reaction mixture changed to dark brown. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into crushed ice and neutralised with ammonia. The solid obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to yield **4a**, (68%), m.p. 158° (Found: C, 31.20; H, 1.30; N, 12.00. $C_9H_7O_3N_3Br_2$ requires: C, 31.30; H, 1.45; N, 12.17%); ν_{max} 3 480–3 200 (NH), 1 680 (C=O) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 5.1 (2H, s, OCH₂), 7.2–7.5 (2H, m, ArH) and 7.8 (1H, br s, NH). For other compounds, mol. formulae, yield (%), m.p. (°C) are: **4b**, $C_9H_7N_3O_2BrCl$, 72, 212; **4c**, 63, 118; **4e**, $C_{10}H_8N_3O_2Br$, 66, 114; **4g**, 75, 96; **4h**, $C_{10}H_7N_3O_2BrCl$, 65, 110.

Antibacterial activity: The results of antibacterial screening indicated that good activity was shown by **3b, c, h** against *S. aureus*, by **3b, c** against *S. aureus* and by **4b, c** against *E. coli*; these compounds also showed moderate activity against *S. typhosa*. All other compounds showed moderate, weak or no activity against the bacterial strains. Two generalisations can be made from these results. Firstly, in comparison with **3a-h**, triazoles **4a-c, e, g, h** were found to be marginally less active and secondly, compounds **3** and **4** with the substitution pattern R/R' = Cl/Br, R'' = H appear to be more active than otherwise substituted compounds.

References

1. D. R. SHRIDHAR, M. JOGIBHUKTA, V. S. H. KRISHNAN, P. P. JOSHI, M. U. R. NAIDU, G. S. THAPAR, A. KRISHNAMURTHY and G. P. THOMAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 1279; D. R. SHRIDHAR, M. JOGIBHUKTA, P. P. JOSHI and P. GOPAL REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 132; D. R. SHRIDHAR, M. JOGIBHUKTA, L. C. VISHWAKARMA, P. P. JOSHI, G. K. A. S. NARAYAN, P. P. SINGH, C. S. RAO and A. V. JUNARKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 445.

2. M. B. HOGALE and N. P. DHORE, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 1985, **9**, 159; M. B. HOGALE, N. P. DHORE and B. P. NIKAM, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 1986, **2**, 111; M. B. HOGALE and B. P. NIKAM, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 735.
3. M. B. HOGALE and B. P. NIKAM, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 1988, **4**, 369.
4. B. ARRET, D. P. JOHNSON and A. KRISHABAUM, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1971, **60**, 1689.

Synthesis of some Substituted 2-Azetidinone and 4-Thiazolidinones

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EARLIER we reported the synthesis and biological activities of various hydrazino derivatives of 1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one¹. Since the β -lactam ring is responsible for the activity of the β -lactam antibiotics whose reactivity is greatly influenced by substituents or fused rings² and since the incorporation of azetidinone or thiazolidinone moiety enhances the biological activity³, we have reported herein the synthesis of various 1,4-benzoxazin-2,3-diones bearing 2-azetidinone and 4-thiazolidinone moieties.

The starting compound 1,4-benzoxazin-2,3-dione was prepared by the method described in literature⁴. This on refluxing with ethyl chloroformate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate gave the 4-carbomethoxy derivative (**1**). On being refluxed with ethanolic hydrazine hydrate, **1** gave the *N*-hydrazides (**2**), which on condensation with various substituted aldehydes produced the Schiff bases (**3**)⁵.

The compounds **3** on condensation with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine produced the corresponding 2-azetidinones (**4**). This cyclocondensation proceeds via ketene intermediate⁶. The action of mercaptoacetic acid on the Schiff bases (**3**) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride yielded the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (**5**).

The compounds have been characterised by ir and nmr data.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

4-Hydrazido-1,4-benzoxazin-2,3-dione (2): A solution of **1** (0.1 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mol) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 h, then excess ethanol removed and the concentrate kept overnight. The resulting crystals were dried and recrystallised from ethanol as colourless

needles, (70%), m.p. 281° (Found : C, 48.82 ; H, 3.10 ; N, 18.91. $C_9H_7O_4N_3$ requires : C, 48.87 ; H, 3.17 ; N, 19.00%) ; ν_{max} 3 200 (NHNH₂), 1 720 (C=O cyclic), 1 665 (C=O acyclic amido) and 1 095 cm^{-1} (C-O-C) ; δ 2.6 (NH₂), 6.8-7.4 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH).

For 3-5, R =

a ; *n*-Pr, **b** ; Ph, **c** ; *o*-C₆H₄OH, **d** ; *m*-C₆H₄OH, **e** ; *p*-C₆H₄OH, **f** ; *p*-C₆H₄OCH₃, **g** ; *o*-C₆H₄Cl, **h** ; *p*-C₆H₄Cl, **i** ; *o*-*p*-C₆H₃Cl₂, **j** ; *m*-C₆H₄NO₂, **k** ; *p*-C₆H₄NO₂, **l** ; *p*-C₆H₄NMe₂, **m** ; CH=CHPh, **n** ; 2-furyl, **o** ; CH=CH-CH₃, **p** ; *m*-C₆H₄N.

Scheme 1

4-Arylidenehydrazido-1,4-benzoxazin-2,3-dione (3) :

To a solution of **2** (0.01 mol) in methanol (30 ml) containing a few drops of glacial acetic acid was added the respective substituted benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The solvent was then distilled off and resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol : **3f**, R=C₆H₄OH (*p*), (70.0%), m.p. 271° (Found : N, 12.32. $C_{17}H_{13}O_5N_3$ requires : N, 12.39%) ; ν_{max} 3 300-3 200 (NH), 1 760 (C=O lactone), 1 680-1 665br (CONH, C=N) and 1 100 cm^{-1} (C-O-C) ; δ 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.6 (1H, s, CH=N), 6.8-7.6 (8H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, br s, CONH). For other compounds (yield) and m.p. (°C) are : **3a**, (76), 176 ; **3b**, (73), 159 ; **3c**, (74), 232 ; **3d**, (72), 265 ; **3e**, (73), 241 ; **3g**, (73), 171 ; **3h**, (75), 242 ; **3i**, (76), 123 ; **3j**, (70), 238 ; **3k**, (71), 163 ; **3l**, (70), 226 ; **3m**, (62), 270 ; **3n**, (67), 221 ; **3o**, (70), 149 ; **3p**, (72), 199.

Preparation of 4a-p : To a well-stirred solution of **3** (0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.002 mol) in dioxane (dry, 25 ml) was added chloroacetyl chloride (0.002 mol) dropwise at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min and then refluxed for 3 h. On removal of dioxane under reduced pressure a solid was obtained which was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol : **4f**, (65%), m.p. 273° (Found : N, 10.03 ; Cl, 8.50, $C_{19}H_{14}O_6N_3Cl$ requires : N, 10.11 ; Cl, 8.54%) ; ν_{max} 3 300-3 250

(NH), 1 780-1 760 (C=O β -lactam), 1 740 (C=O lactone) and 1 680-1 665 cm^{-1} (CONH) ; δ 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.45 (1H, d, *J* 9Hz, CH), 6.25 (1H, d, *J* 9Hz, CHCl), 6.8-7.6 (8H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH). For other compounds (yields) and m.p. (°C) are : **4a**, (68), 221 ; **4b**, (63), 258 ; **4c**, (66), 247 ; **4d**, (66), 227 ; **4e**, (67), 260 ; **4g**, (67), 211 ; **4h**, (68), 221 ; **4i**, (64), 187 ; **4j**, (63), 283 ; **4k**, (61), 260 ; **4l**, (65), 289 ; **4m**, (60), 270 ; **4n**, (65), 269 ; **4o**, (62), 251 ; **4p**, (65), 239.

Preparation of 5a-p : Mercaptoacetic acid (0.001 mol) was added to a well-stirred solution of the Schiff base (**3** ; 0.001 mol) in THF (25 ml). The mixture was stirred for 30 min to 3 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from the proper solvent : **5f**, (64%), m.p. 258° (Found : N, 10.12 ; S, 7.69. $C_{19}H_{15}O_6N_3S$ requires : N, 10.17 ; S, 7.75%) ; ν_{max} 3 300-3 200 (NH), 1 740 (C=O lactone and 5-membered) and 1 665 cm^{-1} (CONH) ; δ 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂-S), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.5 (1H, s, CH), 6.8-7.6 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH). For other compounds (yield) and m.p. (°C) are : **5a**, (66), 273 ; **5b**, (69), 263 ; **5c**, (69), 213 ; **5d**, (70), 271 ; **5e**, (68), 262 ; **5g**, (70), 239 ; **5h**, (70), 279 ; **5i**, (70), 167, **5j**, (69), 271 ; **5k**, (67), 247 ; **5l**, (65), 270 ; **5m**, (63), 260 ; **5n**, (70), 257 ; **5o**, (63), 253 ; **5p**, (67), 276.

References

1. M. B. HOGALE and B. P. NIKAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 735 ; D. B. BOYD, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1983, **26**, 1010 ; M. I. PAGE, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1984, **17**, 144.
2. P. KUMAR C. NATH, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. SHANKER, *Pharmazie*, 1982, **37A**, 11 ; P. KUMAR, P. KUMAR, A. GULATI, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. SHANKER, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1982, **44**, 141.
3. PAXEDDU and SENNA, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1931, **61**, 158.
4. K. MOGILIAH, K. V. REDDY and B. SREENIVASULU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 259.
5. M. A. ABBADT, M. S. EL-KASHEF, A. ABDALLA and N. M. KANDREEL, *J. Chem. Tech. Biotech. (A)* 1984, **34**, 62 ; S. P. HIREMATH, *J. Karnatak Uni. Sci.*, 1974, **14**, 208.

Preparation of some 4-Thiazolidinones as Possible Antimicrobial Agents

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MANY 4-thiazolidinones have been found to possess various pharmacological activities¹. 2,4-Diaminotoluene produces Heinz bodies in the erythrocyte of man and various animals², and it also produces inhibition activity in the growth of Koch